

Eurodoc Annual Report 2022/2023

Brussels, 10 June 2023

Edited by: Eurodoc Board for Eurodoc Administration 2022/2023

Foreword

Dear All,

We live in a genuinely historical time when modern cave barbarism and global threats go hand in hand with unprecedented technological progress. Under these circumstances, the role of science is increasing as we need it to make good decisions in conditions of extreme uncertainty and global turbulence. For science to become a reliable instrument of progress, it has to be trustworthy and oriented toward societal needs. The prerequisite to this is, of course, sustainable academia where fair research culture and academic freedom are in place and researchers are treated adequately at any stage of their careers. The above is what Eurodoc has been advocating for since its inception, and the current Administration made its best to make a decent contribution to our mission. Luckily, thanks to the previous generations of volunteers, today Eurodoc has high visibility among European stakeholders being a change agent and a strong voice of European early career researchers in many international fora.

Advocating for Ukrainian academia in times of war; contributing to the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA); engaging with high-level stakeholders on the topics of Open Science, academic freedom, gender equality, effective doctoral training, and supporting early career researchers were among our notable activities throughout this term. In addition, Eurodoc is now much more active in international collaborations becoming a frequent full partner in project consortia funded under Horizon Europe and Erasmus+ programs. In this report, we provide an overview of the many activities performed during this year. To make it readable, we kept the report as short as possible.

This term is ending, but this is just a new beginning for Eurodoc. We look forward to meeting all of you at the AGM 2023 in person or online and are open to new exciting projects and collaborations. See you in Uppsala!

Eurodoc Administration Board members

*Oleksandr Berezko, Sebastian Dahle,
Hannah Schoch, Danila Rijavec,
Nicola Dengo, Joanna Rutkowska, Patrizia Ferrante*

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1 Eurodoc objectives

Eurodoc shall pursue the following objectives according our [statute](#), [mission and vision](#):

- (a) **To represent** doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
- (b) **To advance** the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
- (c) **To promote** the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, **organize** events, **take part** in debates, and **assist** in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
- (d) **To establish** and **promote** cooperation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

2 Eurodoc Members & Observers

2.1 National Associations (NAs)

Austria (Doktorat.at - OH), Belgium (PhD Society Leuven), Czech Republic (SK RVŠ), Denmark (PAND), Finland (FUURT), France (CJC), Germany (THESIS), Hungary (DOSZ), Ireland (IFUT and USI), Italy (ADI), Latvia (LJZA), Lithuania (LSYR), Netherlands (PNN), Norway (SiN), Poland (KRD), Portugal (ABIC), Romania (ANOSR), Slovakia (ADS), Slovenia (MA), Spain (FJI-Precarios), Sweden (SNPA and SFS/SFSDK), Switzerland (actionuni), Ukraine (RMU), and Azerbaijan (AYSPMU)

2.2 Observers

Individuals: Turkey, Bosnia-Herzegovina

Organisations: Georgia (YSDCG)

Fig. 1 Eurodoc's Members and Observers on a map

3 Eurodoc Administration Members

The Eurodoc administration consists of the Administrative board, Secretariat and Advisory board members.

3.1 Administrative Board

The Administrative Board is Eurodoc's regular executive body who shall represent, lead and administer Eurodoc's daily activities, and also follow the decisions adopted by the General Meeting.

<i>Position</i>	<i>Person</i>	<i>Association</i>
President	Oleksandr Berezko	Ukraine/RMU
Vice-President	Sebastian Dahle	Slovenia/MA
Treasurer	Danila Rijavec	Slovenia/MA
Secretary	Hannah Schoch	Switzerland/actionuni
General Board Member	Nicola Dengo	Italy/ADI
General Board Member	Joanna Rutkowska	Netherlands/PNN
General Board Member	Patrizia Ferrante	Italy/ADI

3.2 Secretariat

Secretariat members are part of the administration who help to carry on the Eurodoc annual goals, coordinated by the Administrative Board.

<i>Position</i>	<i>Person</i>	<i>Association</i>
Secretariat Coordinator	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/SFS/SFSDK
External Communication Coordinator	Anna Pavelieva	Ukraine/RMU
Newsletter Coordinators	Kateryna Hodik	Ukraine/RMU
Language Officer	Maria Zirra & Agbor Takem	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
Webmaster	Khrystyna Zub	Ukraine/RMU
CoE Officer	Beata Zwierzyńska	Poland/KRD
Skills Officer	Nicola Dengo	Italy/ADI
BFUG Officer	Anastasiia Simakhova	Ukraine/RMU
EOSC Officer	Emanuele Storti	Italy/ADI
Gender Equality Officer	Sara Pilia	Italy/ADI
	Elettra Repetto	Italy/ADI

WG Career Development Coordinator	Husam Rajab	Hungary/DOSZ
	Monika Raczynska	Poland/KRD
WG Doctoral Training Coordinator	Karl Kilbo Edlund	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
WG Employment & Welfare Coordinator	Marija Davcheva	Spain/Precarios
WG Mental Health Coordinator	Mathias Schroijsen	Belgium/OR
	Sara Willhammar	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
WG Open Science Coordinator	Maja Dolinar	Slovenia/MA
WG Research & Society Coordinator	Patrizia Ferrante	Italy/ADI
	Natalia Greniewska	Poland/KRD
	Barbora Lekesyte	Lithuania/LSYR
	Larysa Makaruk	Ukraine/RMU
WG Internal Management Coordinators	Pil Maria Saugmann	Sweden/ SFS/SFSDK
	Sara Pilia	Italy/ADI

3.3 Advisory Board

The Advisory Board supports the Administrative board and other Eurodoc bodies with advice and facilitates the knowledge transfer between consecutive terms to assure the continuity of Eurodoc as an organisation.

Advisory board members for 2022/2023:

- Giulia Malaguarnera (Italy)
- Agnieszka Żyra (Poland)
- Iryna Degtyareva (Ukraine)
- Margaux Kersschot (Belgium)
- Farouk Allouche (France)
- Mathias Schroijsen (Belgium)
- Eva Hnátková (Czech Republic)

4 Eurodoc Activities 2022/2023

In this Annual Report, we describe the activities based on Eurodoc's Annual Goals, which were approved by the AGM held in Vilnius (Lithuania) in 2022.

4.1 Developing awareness, policies and outputs on crucial topics for ECRs

4.1.1 Doctoral training

The project "Doctoral Supervision Survey: Good Practices and Recommendations" was recovered by assessing its current status, to identify roadblocks that are preventing it from progressing forward. It was established that a new team had to be assembled to assist Beata Zwierzynska, specifically into discussing the final aspects of the data analysis and establishing the main discussion points that were to be assessed in the final document. This also includes collecting up-to-date relevant bibliographic sources and compiling the introduction. The team is currently being assembled and participants briefed.

Besides this, the working group co-coordinator Karl represented Eurodoc at EUA-CDE's Thematic workshop entitled "[Sustainability in doctoral education: developing a strategic approach](#)", where he also presented on the opportunities and challenges for reducing the carbon footprint of doctoral candidates' mobility.

4.1.2 Research assessment and Career development

The joint statement on research assessment for Early Career Researchers that we intended to produce together with the Marie Curie Alumni Association had been sidelined during the current term by the establishment of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. Our involvement in CoARA includes the establishment of a working group for assessment of Early- and Mid-Career Researchers, that will not only feature our concerns, but produce an overview report on the status quo, approaches to train ECMRs and monitor the impact of the research assessment reform, and finally produce recommendations, tools and guidelines to help improve the situation. With this, the engagement in CoARA far surpasses what could have been achieved with the statement, while also connecting to ongoing projects (OPUS, SECURE).

The project **Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment (SECURE)** launched in January 2023. The project develops coordination and support measures to create, trial, implement, and mainstream a common Research Career Framework (RCF) that offers a suite of options to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers with the aim of improving research careers and reducing career precarity. The RCF will recognise the research profession across sectors, provide a career development and progression structure for research careers, recognise both research and transferable skills and competences, facilitate intersectoral collaboration and mobility, and offer solutions to the precariousness of research careers in academia. It will further develop a range of tenure track-like (TTL) models integrating best practices from existing use cases. The TTL models will offer a variety of options to support organisations employing researchers in sustainable ways for different research career paths. By the time of this report, a large landscaping task was carried out that reviewed several hundred pieces of literature on factors impacting researchers' careers. By the time this report is published, the deliverable has been made available on the project website.¹

¹ Website of the SECURE project: <http://secureproject.eu/>

² Website of the OPUS project: <https://opusproject.eu/>

³ Website of the OPTIMA project: <https://lpnu.ua/en/optima>

4.1.3 Open Science - Eurodoc's engagement in ORE, OPTIMA, and OPUS

Eurodoc is an expert partner in “**Open Research Europe**” (ORE) project, an Open Access Publishing Platform for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, launched in spring 2021 by the European Commission. ORE offers rapid publication of various article types without editorial bias and all submitted articles benefit from transparent peer review and are published under an open license. The platform is a significant step toward Open Science in Europe and the role of Eurodoc is to ensure that the voice of ECRs is heard during its development and implementation. As an expert partner, Eurodoc participates in ORE project team and communication team meetings, organises various events and provides recommendations. In the reporting period Eurodoc particularly organised a [webinar "Discussion on Peer Review"](#) on October 24, 2022 during the Open Access Week and a [Focus Session for the ORE Project](#) in Prague on November 9 during the KRECon 2022 conference. There is a dedicated [ORE portal](#) on the Eurodoc website.

In 2020, in the frames of cooperation with ORE, Eurodoc conducted a survey on publishing in Open Science focused on ECRs to formulate recommendations for ORE. The survey was [published at F1000 as a preprint](#) in 2021. It was planned to finalise the paper during the term, but we were unable to do that due to the high volume of material to process and lack of human resource. We aim at completing the paper by the end of 2023.

Eurodoc is a full partner in the **Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia (OPTIMA)**³ that implements Open Science practices in Ukraine to improve the quality of National higher education services. OPTIMA's priorities include engaging disadvantaged academic communities of displaced Ukrainian universities and focusing on climate action. The main envisioned outputs of the project are the Open Peer Review platform for supporting academic conferences, the implementation of new subjects on Open Science in Ukrainian universities, and the development of an open online course on the topic. The role of Eurodoc in the project is to advise on all the project activities, assist in the creation of an international online community of peer reviewers, and act as speakers and workshop leaders at project events (all on a volunteer basis). Due to the war in Ukraine, OPTIMA was prolonged for one year. Despite that, the project is successful, and Eurodoc's participation is effective. Particularly, in February 2023, OPTIMA's interim technical report was assessed as “very good” (the highest mark) by EACEA.

Eurodoc is also a full partner in the **Open and Universal Science (OPUS)** project that develops coordination and support measures to reform the assessment of research and researchers at Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) towards a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to practice Open Science. For this, OPUS employs a three-tiered approach to ensure representation and consensus building of key stakeholder groups in the Open Science ecosystem via (1) the large project consortium consists of researcher organisations, RPOs, RFOs, industry organisations, and experts in project management, public relations, and Open Science, (2) a series of stakeholder engagement sessions will be held with the broader community to gather input and validate key project deliverables, and (3) an Advisory Board of key representatives will ensure expert oversight and links to the community. By the time this report has been published, Eurodoc has collaborated in the state of the art on Open Science incentives, metrics and indicators, which was published as a deliverable on the project website.

4.2 Contributions from the working groups

4.2.1 Career development

The focus of the working group was according to last year's AGM supposed to be the upcoming reform of assessment of research and researchers, however the working group is somehow misleading as Eurodoc does not have the resources to systematically support the career development of individual doctoral candidates and early career researchers.

In 2023/2024 the WG career development continued working on the “Bullying and Harassment” survey initiated by the former WG Equal opportunities. The survey is scheduled to be launched over the summer.

A note about the process. The work on the survey has been heavily supported and to some degree also carried out by members of the board, the secretariat coordinator, the equal opportunity officer, the wg mental health and a past wg open science coordinator.

Considering the long processes that have surrounded other surveys that Eurodoc has conducted in the past, it raises the question about when Eurodoc should carry out surveys and how the analysis of such surveys should be handled. To avoid a repetition of the situation around the postdoc survey the board of Eurodoc recommends that data from the survey is analyzed by a taskforce and that the coordinator of this taskforce is appointed by the new board. Any one who has been active in the drafting process of the survey will of-course be invited to participate in this task force, as well as all NAs will be invited to appoint someone for it as well.

4.2.2 Doctoral training

The WG Doctoral training has throughout the year worked on a statement on what constitutes a doctoral degree. The is divided into three parts, a parts that concerns the skills that doctoral candidates acquired throughout their education, a section about which prerequisites, financial resources as well as other resources, need to be in place for doctoral candidates to have sufficient conditions throughout their education, and a section about how doctoral education should be quality assured.

4.2.3 Employment and welfare

The WG employment and welfare has drafted a statement for Eurodoc to articulate its opinions on what constitutes “High quality employment conditions for early career researchers”. The statement will be published shortly into the next term.

4.2.4 Open science

The Open Science WG has drafted a statement for Eurodoc to articulate its opinions on open science, which will be published shortly into the next term.

4.2.5 Research and society

The Research and Society WG has contributed greatly to the discussions on Academic Freedom, and has transferred the corresponding discussions into two statements, one of which has been published already, the other being close to publication. Besides this the working group has discussed research ethics and integrity.

4.2.6 Mental health

The mental health WG started the year by going through the Eurodoc statement on mental health and the ReMO manifesto. The WG has also contributed to updating the WG webpage and the release text for the mental health statement as well as discussed what a potential follow-up article could include. During the second part of the year, the WG has focused on creating a slide set that can be used by NAs when addressing mental health issues on a national level. Besides this, the WG has been represented in the ReMO network and discussed their upcoming survey and the dissemination thereof.

Besides this the working group has written an article for the Eurodoc webpage and contributed to the drafting of the panel session “**A sustainable academic psychosocial work environment**” at the Eurodoc conference 2023 “A sustainable academia”.

4.3 Lobby for policy and/or cultural changes of profound importance to ECRs

4.3.1 Employment status and working conditions for ECRs in Europe

The employment status and working conditions has been a focus of Eurodoc's work during the past term. We contributed to and endorsed the [Manifesto for Early-Career Researchers](#), which we handed over in person to Commissioner Mariya Gabriel together with colleagues from the Marie Curie Alumni Association, Young Academy of Europe, and Association of ERC Grantees, as well as with the Initiative for Science in Europe, who organized the event. We engaged specific country cases upon request, such as the Italian one covered within a [Statement on the reintroduction of detrimental policies](#) in Italy. Further, Eurodoc has throughout the year put focus on ECR with parenting responsibilities with both an article "[Pregnancy, parenting and precarity](#)" published on March 8th and by [endorsing Mothers in Science](#) later in May. Finally, the topic is at the core of the project SECURE, in which Eurodoc participates as a full partner and beneficiary.

4.3.2 Adequate training, rewarding system and implementation of Open Science instruments for ECRs

Open Science has continued as a focus topic for Eurodoc, and during the term, we collaborated in a number of works together with our partners and stakeholders, including a Joint Statement on the EU Council conclusions on Research Assessment and the Implementation of Open Science, and a Joint Statement on the high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing. Further activities towards policy and cultural change regarding Open Science include the online panel discussion on Open Peer Review and the in-person workshop on Open Research Europe, that Eurodoc has organised. Rewarding and implementing Open Science is the core content of the project OPUS, in which Eurodoc participates as a full partner.

4.3.3 Academic freedom as a fundamental right for researchers

Academic freedom is a fundamental necessity for researchers, yet if we look across Europe we see that it is challenged in many places in many different ways. Early career researchers are due to their precarious working conditions often especially vulnerable to challenges and attacks to the academic freedom of researchers. In the past two years Eurodoc has had an increased focus on academic freedom, raising awareness about how academic freedom must extend to doctoral candidates and early career researchers, and what can be done to strengthen the academic freedom of those.

The advocacy work surrounding this has included several dimensions. Oleksandr Berzko has in his capacity as president of Eurodoc participated in two events on the topic of academic freedom organised by the European Parliament, namely the conference [EP4AcademicFreedom event in November](#) and round table discussion in April [EP roundtable](#).

Simultaneously, Eurodoc has finalized the first of two planned statements on the topic of academic freedom. This statement focuses on the governmental and institutional responsibility in guaranteeing the academic freedom of researchers, especially ECRs. The statement can be found here [First AF statement](#)

The second statement is still in preparation, but will be finalized and published in the term 2023/2024.

With regard to academic freedom, Eurodoc has also responded to the Academic Freedom monitor published by the European Parliament's Panel for the Future of Science and Technology. For this, feedback was taken in from the national associations and published as a discussion thread on the Social Media channels.

Moreover, Eurodoc has led the publication of a joint response together with Marie Curie Alumni Association, Young Academy of Europe, and the International Consortium of Research Staff Associations, commenting on the situation of researchers in Iran and other authoritarian contexts. The four organisations continue working together to complete a deep analysis of the needs that can be

addressed through the different structures and capacities of each organisation. You can read the full statement [here](#).

Eurodoc's focus on academic freedom is likely to continue the coming year. This will include the analysis of the data generated by the joint survey with MCAA and YAE on the situation of Iranian academics, the finalization of a second academic freedom statement focusing on the rights and responsibility of individual researchers.

4.3.4 Support Ukrainian researchers in the time of war and as long as it is needed

Eurodoc stands in solidarity with the people of Ukraine and fully condemns Russia's aggressive war against this country. As part of the international movement of doctoral candidates and researchers at all career stages, we are particularly concerned for all students, doctoral candidates, and other researchers affiliated with academic institutions and other research facilities of Ukraine. It is important to recognize that this war is not a war solely on Ukraine, it is also an attack on democracy and on the idea of a free and peaceful world. The research and higher education sector in Europe must with renewed urgency continue to do its utmost to support Ukrainian universities, researchers, and students such that they can safely continue their research and studies in Ukraine or elsewhere. Right after the war had started, Eurodoc created a [special task force](#) that is dedicated to supporting our Ukrainian colleagues as best as we can.

Eurodoc, as a pan-European network, that engages with the key stakeholders in the EU and beyond, is in the position to advocate for specific measures to support Ukraine and its academia at the highest level. Accordingly, the task force analysed the current needs of the Ukrainian research and education systems and published an [open letter to Mariya Gabriel](#), then-Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth on supporting Ukrainian academia during and after the war, which included specific recommendations and call for action. The open letter was also handed to the Commissioner in person. Eurodoc believes that the formulated recommendations remain relevant and plan further steps concerning their practical implementation, particularly regarding involving Ukrainian entities in EU-funded grants, which was also discussed at other fora, e.g. during the online Digital Theme UK-Ukraine Research Twinning Conference during 27-30 March 2023.

In addition to advocacy and coordination work, Eurodoc participated in the relevant grant proposal preparation and submission process. As Russia's invasion devastates Ukraine and its academia, causing an urgent need to ensure resilience and sustainable economic growth, it is important to empower the war-affected Ukrainian research and higher education systems by adopting the UNESCO recommendation on open science, thus fostering digital transformation and enhancing higher education performance in many directions. This urgency is increased due to the need to make the most of the current opportunity window for Ukrainian society. As Ukraine lacks domestic expertise in open and digital science and is extremely limited in resources, knowledge transfer, supervision, and support by external funding are crucial for ensuring progress. To address this, Eurodoc became a full partner in the structural project proposal Open4UA (Erasmus+ KA2) aimed at fostering the reform on Open Science in Ukraine and introducing advanced approaches and mechanisms of research assessment prioritising Open Science at national and institutional levels.

4.4 Engagement of stakeholders/partners on Eurodoc's key topics

4.4.1 Contributing in policy statements on relevant topics for Eurodoc

As identified by the administrative board of Eurodoc 2021/2022 there is an increasing need for Eurodoc to collect and present its fundamental opinions in a comprehensive manner. For this reason, many of the working groups have in the last year worked on producing policy statements, such as the WG Mental Health did in 2021/2022. This has led to the writing of three new policy statements written by the working groups. Two of these have recently passed through consultation, while the third one "The doctoral

education - a research education" will be presented at the AGM before being discussed at consultation over the summer.

4.4.2 Representatives to task forces at the Initiative for Science in Europe

Through the Initiative of Science in Europe (ISE) Eurodoc is represented in many different European task forces and working groups, such as the ERA Forum, an expert group informing the European Commission. This provides Eurodoc the opportunity to voice the opinions of Early Career Researchers to stakeholders and policymakers at a European level, either directly or indirectly through representatives of other member organizations of ISE.

For this reason Eurodoc prioritizes contributing to the work of ISE highly, and supports this work both by nominating representatives for task forces and working groups in ERA, as well as for the supportive task forces within ISE itself.

4.4.3 Attending relevant stakeholder events and justifying relevance to NAs

Eurodoc has throughout the year attended a number of stakeholder events, such as meetings in ISE, Science Business, and EUA-CDE. When participating in such events a mission report is filed, and in many cases an article is written for the Eurodoc webpage.

A task for next year is, in connection with the stakeholder analysis, to communicate more intuitively what Eurodoc's contributions are in these collaborations and how Eurodoc, the NAs and/or ECRs are expected to benefit directly or indirectly from these.

4.4.4 Engaging stakeholders in projects and events organised by Eurodoc

In the context of Open Science, Eurodoc organized an online panel discussion about Open Peer Review on October 24, 2022. Further engagements on Open Science were achieved through the workshop Eurodoc organized with Open Research Europe in November 2022.

With regards to academic freedom and the specificities of different national research areas, Eurodoc organized a webinar about the Academic values in Hungary, Poland, Slovenia and Ukraine on January 24, 2023.

Furthermore, a number of stakeholders have been invited to participate in the Lunchtime seminars for ECRs, where seminars has been given by [CRAC-VITAE](#), Project [Retain](#), Project [RoSiE](#) and the executive coordinator [Monica Dietl](#) of ISE.

4.5 Increase visibility of Eurodoc to remain as a relevant stakeholder and partner

4.5.1 Participating in and contributing to work done by the European Commission, Council of Europe, and other relevant stakeholders

The contribution to work by the European Commission has mainly happened through the ERA Forum stakeholder group, through its public consultations, as well as through joint efforts e.g. with the Initiative for Science in Europe.

During the term 2022/2023, Eurodoc board members have participated in events at the European Parliament, organised by the EP Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA), namely the establishment of the EP Forum for Academic Freedom in November and a roundtable discussion on Academic Freedom in April.

Eurodoc represents ECRs towards the Council of Europe in both the Conference of International NGOs ([CINGO](#)) of which Eurodoc is a member and in the Steering Committee of Education ([CD-EDU](#)) of which Eurodoc is an observer. In both organizations Eurodoc has in the past year advocated for the importance of academic freedom, the role of research and higher education in the recovery of Ukraine, and for an increased focus on equal opportunities.

Eurodoc is a member of the Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE), and through ISE Eurodoc has in the last year been a driving factor in the writing of the “[A Manifesto for Early Career Researchers](#)”, a statement that puts focus on the conditions of early career researchers. The statement can be endorsed by both organizations and individuals [here](#). ISE and the member organisations of ISE are some of Eurodocs closest collaborators, and many of the members of ISE are among those organisations with whom Eurodoc collaborates in also CoARA.

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking research in Europe. During the term, Eurodoc has exchanged with Science Europe on several occasions and has taken part as an invited guest at the event “Science-Policy in Actions for the Green and Digital Transition”.

Eurodoc actively advocates the conditions of doctoral candidates and early career researchers towards and number of university organisations, the largest of these being the European University Association (EUA) and in particular it Council on Doctoral Education (EUA-CDU). In the past year, Eurodoc has presented at both the annual EUA-CDU conference in Manchester (United Kingdom) as well as the at the meeting in Timisura (Romania).

4.5.2 Eurodoc in the media and on social media

Eurodoc’s social media profiles are used to promote statements, surveys, and policy input from Eurodoc and others. Similarly Eurodoc cultivates a relationship with stakeholders on social media by following and sharing relevant posts of collaborators and others. This is a deliberate strategy from Eurodoc as many of our collaborators are organizations similar to Eurodoc where the first few likes and reposts are crucial for how far a story makes it.

Since the last AGM in Vilnius Eurodoc has published around 50 articles on the webpage, which corresponds to roughly one per week. These articles are reposted and shared on all Eurodoc’s social media accounts, meaning that Eurodoc publishes regularly on both the website and on social media accounts. Eurodoc has reached a threshold in terms of the number of articles published by Eurodoc which allows for a long term publishing strategy ensuring a good spread throughout the year.

The articles that are written for Eurodoc’s webpage in general aim to raise awareness on Eurodoc’s work in particular and the conditions of doctoral candidates and early career researchers conditions more generally. Some, examples of such articles has for included articles in the “Meet the NA’s series” (see e.g. [Germany](#), [Czech](#), [Spain](#)), articles from WG’s such as this one from the WG Mental health, articles about Eurodoc statements such as this one about the academic freedom statement, articles from meetings and conference where Eurodoc is represented such as [this one](#) from December about the conference “[Ending Gender-Based Violence in Academia](#),”

Eurodoc has through the last year imposed a policy for how articles should be signed and have started implementing that one signs by including one’s orcid number. This is done to ensure that all who contribute to the writing are credited in a transparent manner.

4.5.3 Eurodoc Annual Conference

Eurodoc Conference 2023 titled “A Sustainable Academia”, focused on how to create sustainable conditions for doctoral candidates and early-career researchers, was held in Uppsala, Sweden from the 7th-8th of June 2023. The event was co-organized by four organisations Eurodoc, the two Swedish NAs SNPA, SFS/SFS-DK and a Swedish trade union for civil servants Fackförbundet ST within the university sector.

The aim of the event was to bring together different actors within the sector of research and higher education in order to discuss different aspects of how to create sustainable conditions for doctoral candidates and early career researchers. To address all the issues mentioned before the conference had seven panel sessions and a number of keynote speakers.

4.6 Improving a sustainable internal Eurodoc governance.

4.6.1 Improving internal communication and cooperation between the NAs: with each other and with Eurodoc.

Eurodoc has during this term continued the increased focus on more dialogue between the Eurodoc administration and the National associations, first and foremost by continuing the NA meetings.

In 2023/2024 Eurodoc has held 5 NA meetings. These meetings are structured such that they require little preparation from the NAs. The focus of the meetings are to include the NAs more easily in ongoing discussions, as well as to provide information about ongoing issues in Eurodoc. The meetings are informal and have no decision making power, notes and presentations are shared afterwards, but no formal minutes are taken. Some NAs have asked for proper minutes, however, it is a balance where also the workload of the members of the Eurodoc administration has to be taken into account.

It is the board's recommendation that the WG internal management continues to be responsible for the hosting of the NA meetings. The board recommends that the coordination of the WG internal management is handled by the Secretariat Coordinator, the Gender Equality Officer and a(nother) member of the board of administrative board of Eurodoc.

The Eurodoc administration has also on several occasions presented the work of Eurodoc to various NAs. These presentations happened on request of the NAs, however, based on the experience of the presenters, these presentations should be offered to all NAs.

4.6.2 Improving the management of the External communication team

The internal processes of the communication team have been streamlined to simplify the work and to enhance the input from all members of the Eurodoc administration. This has led to an increased volume of outputs, more online engagement, and has rendered it possible to be present on Instagram as another social media platform. During this period of time the External Communication team has published 47 articles on the website, posts in all 4 social media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram), has launched the "Eurodoc Family" campaign (dedicated to the activities of the National Associations), started the series of articles, dedicated to the Board Members (to be continued in 2023/2024), launched the Instagram account (with 90 posts as of May 30th, 2023).

The External Communication team has assisted Pil Maria Saugmann and Sara Pilia with the Instagram Campaign "Women in Science".

The External Communication Team, in addition to other tasks, is going to continue the series of articles, dedicated to the Board members, the "Eurodoc family" series and the one, planned by Pil Maria Saugmann, dedicated to Ukrainian academia in times of war, as well as enhance communication and cooperation with Eurodoc's stakeholders.

4.6.3 Gender Equality Plan

In 2022/2023 the first gender equality for Eurodoc has been drafted for the AGM to discuss and vote upon. The gender equality plan should be looked over annually, and the recommendation is that it in 2023/2024 is supplemented by a code of conduct.

4.6.4 Defining criteria for selecting projects in which Eurodoc may contribute as a partner or advisory board member (in line with Eurodoc mission and vision)

The board has drafted a guideline based on the statutes, internal regulations and other public documents that will be discussed at the AGM 2023, amended in the coming mandate together with the Code of Conduct, and will be voted upon at AGM 2024.

4.6.5 Preparing detailed criteria which describe the process of recruiting people to work on European external projects in which Eurodoc is a partner

The board has reviewed relevant documents such as the European Charter for Researchers and the European Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, as well as a number of institutional policies and regulations. Although the positions in Eurodoc are no research positions, the board decided that the same strict criteria and processes should be applied as for any research-performing organisation, in order to lead by example. The process is thus designed to be handled by a recruitment committee, making all steps transparent and objective, documenting the processes in line with GDPR requirements, and providing an objective ranking and suggestion to be voted upon by the board. The final decision is taken by the board according to the statutes. Since the employment decision does likely exceed the mandate of the board, it is all the more important that the process is followed well, and that the initial selection of the project participation is well carried out according to agreed and well-defined transparent criteria. Templates are provided to the board to ensure a coherent documentation by future recruitment committees. The full description of the employment process can be found on the Eurodoc website.

4.6.6 Creating guidelines/criteria for NAs for preparing Eurodoc conference

Together with this years organizer of the Eurodoc conference, a basic overview on the requirements for preparing the Eurodoc annual conference and annual general meeting was produced. These are typically to be organized on 4 consecutive days, e.g. the conference on Wednesday and Thursday and the AGM on Friday and Saturday. Thus, the organizers have to:

- Cover the accommodation -- hotels for invited speakers, hostels for Eurodoc's participants, for at least three nights, including an assistance to Eurodoc with bookings
- Arrange the catering – including lunch on all four days and at least a conference dinner on one evening, ideally with dinner on all days
- Provide travel information
- Arrange the financial agreement to either transfer the funds to Eurodoc or provide information about how to receive payments from extra participants and how reimburse the travel costs of invited speakers and Eurodoc delegates
- Arrange a Conference venue for both days of the conference (room for min. 120 people)
- Arrange a venue for both day of the AGM (room for 75 people)
- Arrange appropriate IT services (internet connectivity suitable for streaming and hybrid participation; presentation equipment for the conference; videoconferencing equipment for the AGM)

All these points should be addressed in writing through an application provided during the previous year no later than October 1st.

4.6.7 Continue monitoring the situation in Ukraine and keep the Ukrainian Task Force as long as it is needed

The taskforce has throughout the year worked in collaboration with the board and administration through the year. The input from the taskforce helped this year's and last year's board and advisory board members formulate [a letter](#) they released on the 24th of February . The last meeting was held in April 2023, and the taskforce will be happy to welcome new members from the NAs after the summer.

It is the board's recommendation that the Ukraine Taskforce continues. Specifically it is needed that the taskforce continues to help Eurodoc put focus on the consequences of the war on Ukrainian early career researchers and supports Eurodoc in identifying how Eurodoc can support that research and higher education plays a central role in the recovery of Ukraine.

4.6.8 Annual Questionnaire

Eurodoc has during the last many years conducted an annual questionnaire. In 2022/2023 the annual questionnaire has undergone a few smaller changes. This has been done in order to ensure that the outcome of the AQ to a larger degree can be used by Eurodoc. The questionnaire provides the members of Eurodoc with the opportunity of voicing the opinions on what Eurodoc should focus on during the next term.

5 Eurodoc Representations and Missions in 2022/2023

Eurodoc representatives contributed to many conferences, meetings, and events. We tried to list all of them in the table below. You can find short descriptions and further information [here](#).

Name of the Eurodoc representative	Event	Date	Place/form
Sebastian Dahle	“ERC Workshop on Research Assessment” European Research Council Executive Agency	June 14+15, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“First PhD Supervision Excellence Training for Academic Staff” E-NOTE, European Network On Teaching Excellence	June 20, 2022	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“European Education and Innovation Summit” European Commission	June 23, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“Annual Meeting” EUA-CDE	June 23, 2022	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“3rd Stakeholder Assembly Meeting on the Reform of Research Assessment” Science Europe & EUA	July 8, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“Summer School of a Young Scientist 3.0” RMU	August 18, 2022	Online
Nicola Dengo	“KE-ERA study: ‘Strengthening research careers: a focus on competences, balanced talent circulation and intersectoral mobility’” European Commission / IDEA Consult	September 12, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	"Polish-Ukrainian Summer Camp for Young Scientists" KRD and RMU	September 12, 2022	Online
Sebastian Dahle Oleksandr Berezko	“OPUS project Kick-off Meeting” PLOCAN (OPUS project coordinator)	September 19+20, 2022	Gran Canaria, Spain
Oleksandr Berezko	“Science Summit” United Nations General Assembly (UNGA77)	September 30, 2022	Online
Sara Pilia	“General Assembly”; CoE	October 05+06, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	Board meeting of the Doctoral candidates’ Forum of Polish Universities	October 08, 2022	Online

Sebastian Dahle	“4th Stakeholder Assembly Meeting on the Reform of Research Assessment” Science Europe & EUA	October 13, 2022	Online
Joanna Rutkowska	“Co-creation workshop on the epistemic responsibilities of the universities” Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam researcher team led by Iris Lechner	October 18, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“Expected outcomes: What should research assessment reform aim to deliver, and how to get there?” Science Business in partnership with Elsevier	October 25, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	Meeting with doctoral candidates of the University of Zaragoza (Spain) and of the University of Pau and the Adour Region (France) University of Zaragoza	October 27, 2022	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“Open Science event 2022” Young Academy of Slovenia	October 27, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	Discussion panel "PhD student as doctoral student in the world - the role of international cooperation in educating doctoral students and conducting research"; Warsaw Doctoral Students' Association	November 19, 2022	Online
Joanna Rutkowska	“International workshop on the research workforce of the future: Promoting diverse career options for doctoral and postdoctoral researchers (first day only)” OECD global science forum	November 22, 2022	Online
Sara Pilia	“Ending Gender-Based Violence in academia” Centre for Gender and Science - Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences	November 24+25, 2022	Prague
Sebastian Dahle	“STOA High-level conference ‘How to provide enforceable protection for academic freedom at EU level?’” European Parliament, Panel for the Future of Science and Technology (STOA)	November 28, 2022	Brussels, Belgium
Nicola Dengo	“Higher Education Sector Observatory Workshop (2nd Workshop)” Technopolis Group	November 29, 2022	Online

Oleksandr Berezko	OpenAIRE Strategy launch, OpenAIRE	November 29, 2022	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“Public roundtable after the Constitutive Assembly of the CoARA coalition” EUA & Science Europe	December 01, 2022	Brussels, Belgium
Oleksandr Berezko, Sebastian Dahle	“Constitutive Assembly of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)” EUA & Science Europe	December 01, 2022	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“Pan-European Digital Assets Supporting Research Communities” EOSC Future/07 Projects Webinar	December 06, 2022	Online
Joanna Rutkowska	“Co-creation workshop on the epistemic responsibilities of the universities” Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam researcher team led by Iris Lechner	December 14, 2022	Amsterdam, the Netherlands
Sebastian Dahle	“Ceremonial handover of the ISE Manifesto for Early Career Researchers to European Commissioner Mariya Gabriel” European Commission, Initiative for Science in Europe	January 10, 2023	Brussels, Belgium
Nicola Dengo	“Improving training and career progression of doctoral candidates” EUF - European University Foundation	January 18, 2023	Online
Karl Kilbo Edlund	“EUA-CDE Thematic Workshop– Sustainability in doctoral education: developing a strategic approach” EUA-CDE	January 19- 23, 2023	Cluj Napoca, Romania
Oleksandr Berezko	“Digital Theme Ambassadors Coordination meeting” University of Liverpool, UK	January 24, 2023	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“Kick-off meeting for the SECURE project” Platforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN)	January 26+27, 2023	Telde, Gran Canaria, Spain
Oleksandr Berezko	“Digital transformation of scientific activities of higher education institutions in the context of European integration” Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine	January 31, 2023	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	Conference “Modern Doctoral Training: exchange of experience and best practices” Ternopil National Medical University	February 02, 2023	Online

Sara Pilia	“Annual Conference”; VOICES COST action	February 14+15, 2023	Malta
Sebastian Dahle (in person), Sara Pilia (online)	“MCAA Annual Conference” Marie Curie Alumni Association	February 24+25, 2023	Cordoba, Spain
Oleksandr Berezko	“Open Science Retreat” Leibniz Information Centre for Economics	March 21, 2023	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“Science-Policy in Actions for the Green and Digital Transition” ScienceEurope	March 29, 2023	Brussels, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle, Pii Maria Saugmann	“Policy discussion workshop & General Assembly” Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE)	March 30+31, 2023	Brussels, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle	“The Road to Research Assessment Reform in Europe” Clarivate / Research Professional news	April 04, 2023	Online
Pii Maria Saugmann	“CD–EDU meeting”	April 3-5, 2023	Strasbourg
Sara Pilia	“25 years celebration conference of ADI”; ADI	April 14-16, 2023	Bologna
Pii Maria Saugmann	“INSPIRE Workshop” INSPIRE	April 19, 2023	Online
Sebastian Dahle	“Annual Researcher Career Summit” ICoRSA	April 20, 2023	Online
Pii Maria Saugmann	“Annual Meeting” PAND	April 21, 2023	Online
Joanna Rutkowska, Sara Pilia	VOICES of Europe	April 24+25, 2023	Online
Pii Maria Saugmann, Sara Pilia	“General Assembly of the Conference of INGOs (CINGO) - Spring Session. + General Assembly of INGO service” CINGO	April 24-26, 2023	Online
Oleksandr Berezko	“STOA (Panel for the Future of Science and Technology of the European Parliament) Roundtable on Academic Freedom” European Parliament	April 27, 2023	Brussels, Belgium
Sebastian Dahle	“Frontiers Forum Live 2023”	April 27-29, 2023	Online
Pii Maria Saugmann	“Academic Freedom in a New Era Conference” Sveriges Unga Akademi (SUA)	May 04, 2023	Online
Nicola Dengo	“PRIDE Annual Conference 2023: Research Conduct and Integrity - the Challenges for the Doctoral	May 04+05, 2023	Porto, Portugal

	Journey" PRIDE Network		
Pil Maria Saugmann	"The Wenner-Gren Foundations International Symposium: Publishing in Academia: Digital Challenges"	May 10-12, 2023	Stockholm
Oleksandr Berezko	"Open Science: Transparency and Availability of Information on Scientific Research" Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine	May 12, 2023	Online
Sara Pilia	"VOICES of Europe—core group meeting" VOICES COST action	May 16, 2023	Online
Sebastian Dahle	"Philipp Schwartz and Inspireurope Stakeholder Forum" Alexander von Humboldt foundation, Scholars at Risk, InspirEurope	May 23+24, 2023	Berlin

6 Eurodoc External Communication

6.1 Website

The Eurodoc website during the reporting period (Jun 11, 2022 – June 1, 2023) gained comparable popularity to the previous period, receiving in total ca. 27k users and around 59k pageviews (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Eurodoc website popularity (print screen from Google Analytics)

The most common website users' age group was people between 25 and 34 years of age (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Age of Eurodoc website audience (print screen from Google Analytics)

Most website visitors came from: USA (13.74%), Germany (12.26%), UK (7.07%), China (6.60%), France (4.95%), Italy (4.79%), , Netherlands (2.97%), Spain (2.94%), Sweden (2.71%) and India (2.50%). Small numbers of people from a large number of other countries then formed a “[long tail](#)” of 43.8% of visitors.

Throughout the year, several initiatives have been made to improve communication in Eurodoc. This includes:

The dissemination of participation of Eurodoc Board Members in various conferences and scientific events:

- ❖ [Eurodoc participated in STOA Academic Freedom Roundtable](#)
- ❖ [Eurodoc Participated in the SECURE Project Kick-Off Meeting](#)
- ❖ [Ceremonial handover of the ISE Manifesto for young research careers to European commissioner Mariya Gabriel](#)

In-person communication during the Board meeting, ORE session and KRECon 2022 Conference in Prague:

- ❖ [Eurodoc's In-Person Board Meeting Takes Place in Prague](#)
- ❖ [Eurodoc Delegation Participated in the KRECon 2022 Conference](#)
- ❖ [Eurodoc held a focus session for the Open Research Europe \(ORE\) project in Prague](#)

Launch of a series of articles, dedicated to the Board Members 2022/2023 (intended to be continued in 2023/2024): [Interview with Pil Maria Saugmann on International Volunteering and the Role of Eurodoc Working Groups](#):

47 articles were published on the Eurodoc's website. The themes of the articles were diverse but relevant, relating to:

- ❖ Webinars:
 - [Save the date - Eurodoc Lunchtime seminar on Science Policy](#),
 - [Webinar on February 28: Surprising Insights from a Fellow Eurodocer's Unusual Career Path](#),
 - [Eurodoc Webinar "Academic values: Approaches in Hungary, Poland, Slovenia, and Ukraine"](#),
 - Eurodoc Webinar "Discussion on Peer Review" during the Open Access Week 2022,
- ❖ Congratulations:
 - [Happy Easter 2023 from Eurodoc!](#),
 - [Eurodoc turns 21. Happy birthday to us!](#),
 - [Merry Christmas and Happy New Year 2023!](#),
- ❖ Statements:
 - [Eurodoc on Mariya Gabriel's Resignation](#),
 - [Eurodoc Endorses the Mothers-in-Science Action Plan](#),
 - [Eurodoc Statement on Academic Freedom](#),
 - [Eurodoc, ICoRSA, MCAA and YAE publish a Joint statement on the Current Situation of Researchers in Iran and other authoritarian contexts](#),
 - [Earthquake disaster in Turkey and Syria](#),
 - [Eurodoc Statement on the Italian Government's Reintroduction of the "Assegni di Ricerca" Scholarship Scheme](#),
 - [Joint Open Letter to European Commissioner Mariya Gabriel on Supporting Ukrainian Academia During and After the War](#),
 - [Joint Statement on the EU Council conclusions on Research Assessment and the Implementation of Open Science](#),
- ❖ Interviews:
 - [Interview with Joeri Tjink on How to Survive and Stay Happy in Academia](#),
 - [Interview with Pil Maria Saugmann on International Volunteering and the Role of Eurodoc Working Groups](#),
- ❖ Articles:
 - [Precarity and parenthood: why Eurodoc endorses Mothers in Science](#),
 - [Eurodoc participated in STOA Academic Freedom Roundtable](#),
 - [Academic freedom concerns all researchers - and the discussion thus must include doctoral candidates and early-career researchers](#),
 - [Remember the Ukrainian Academia: the war on Ukraine is a war on democracy in Europe, human rights, and academic freedom](#),
 - [Eurodoc Launches its "Women in Research" Campaign, How are you feeling? Introducing simple principles and acts fostering healthy work environments](#),

- [Eurodoc Participated in the SECURE Project Kick-Off Meeting,](#)
 - [Let's talk about \(doctoral\) education,](#)
 - [Eurodoc Women in Research Campaign,](#)
 - [Ceremonial handover of the ISE Manifesto for young research careers to European commissioner Mariya Gabriel,](#)
 - [Boldness required: to end gender-based violence, we need to change academia altogether,](#)
 - [STOA Conference 2022 – Academic Freedom in Europe,](#)
 - [Eurodoc participated in the Constitutive Assembly of the CoARA Coalition,](#)
 - [Eurodoc Delegation Participated in the KRECon 2022 Conference,](#)
 - [Eurodoc held a focus session for the Open Research Europe \(ORE\) project in Prague,](#)
 - [Linking research, advocacy and societal challenges – Eurodoc within the Conference of INGOs of the Council of Europe,](#)
 - [Eurodoc's In-Person Board Meeting Takes Place in Prague,](#)
 - [Eurodoc participated in the OPUS Project Kick-Off Conference,](#)
 - [Official launch of signing the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment,](#)
 - [Eurodoc Signed the Manifesto for Early Career Researchers,](#)
 - [Eurodoc to participate in OPUS project supporting changes in research assessment to reward Open Science practices,](#)
 - [The Guide to a Doctorate in France Helps PhD Candidates in Reaching Their "Destinations" Worldwide,](#)
 - [PRESS RELEASE: Eurodoc to sign the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and to Join the Coalition in its Constitutive Assembly,](#)
 - [Doing a doctorate in Ukraine: time and timing in times of war.](#)
- ❖ Vacancies:
 - [Eurodoc Vacancy: Team Member in the OPUS Project,](#)
 - [Eurodoc position vacancy: team member position as a part of the Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment \(SECURE\) project,](#)
 - [Pregnancy, Parental Leave and Precarity Or Obstacles for Early Career Researchers With Children,](#)
 - [Open Call for Early Career Researchers: Focus Session for the ORE Project in Prague.](#)
 - ❖ Series of articles, dedicated to the NAs:
 - [Thesis on Addressing the Challenges of ECRs in Germany;](#)
 - [The Czech Republic on Reform of Doctoral Studies;](#)
 - [Federación de Jóvenes Investigadores \(FJI/ Precarios\) on addressing the challenges of ECRs in Spain; Confederation of Young Researchers on addressing the challenges of ECRs in France](#)

6.2 Social Media

Our followership grew on social media from July 2022 to June 2023.

- Facebook page followers grew from 6 911 to 7179 (+3.9%) for the previous year; for the last 28 days: there were 22 new posts, the account audience was 5 670 users, it received 285 likes, and 42 shares.
- Twitter followers grew from 6072 to 6429 (+5.9%); there were 520 new tweets/retweets (as of May 21st, 2023).
- LinkedIn followers grew from 2 824 to 3 415 (+20.9%); there were 199 new posts, the account got 1 949 page views and 949 unique visitors.

- The YouTube account grew from 92 to 120 subscribers (+30%); there were 9 new videos, the account received 1 500 views and 99.6 hours of watch time.
- Instagram account was created on January 22, 2023; there were 82 new posts and the account got 117 followers.

6.3 Newsletters

The Eurodoc Newsletter is an important part of Eurodoc's communication activities, particularly towards external stakeholders, but, due to the difficult working conditions (continuous missile and drone attacks), the Eurodoc Newsletter Officer Kateryna Hodik, who is from Kyiv, was able to prepare only 3 issues.

7 Special Thanks from the President

I want to thank our whole community and network of partners for this long, challenging, and fruitful year full of inspiring collaboration with many great people inside and outside Eurodoc! We appreciate the effort of every person who contributes their time and skill to make Academia (and the world) a better place through Eurodoc by co-creating statements and policy inputs, joining discussions, and spreading the word.

For me, this term started in a rural village in the Ukrainian Carpathians where I came to ensure my uninterrupted online participation in the Eurodoc Conference and AGM 2022 as at that time Ukrainian cities were under constant threat of Russian shellings. And from the very first days, I realised that our team is not only knowledgeable and professional, but is highly motivated and not afraid of setting the bar high for Eurodoc.

Of course, when I decided to run for the Presidency late in 2021, I couldn't imagine the circumstances of 2022 and beyond. However, the war-caused limitations (e.g., inability to cross the border) and uncertainty (e.g., numerous air raid alerts and frequent blackouts) were only the "technical" challenges. If you ever run for a Eurodoc President position, please be prepared to quickly become a multi-tasking expert in a wide range of important topics demanding your urgent attention, which have never been your primary foci. I am grateful to all the members of the Eurodoc administration 2022/2023 that during my whole term, I had a constant feeling of being surrounded by like-minded colleagues ready to give a helping hand and provide top-level expertise on any complicated topic.

In 2014 I was responsible for Ukraine's admission to Eurodoc and have been involved in various capacities since: as a delegate, webmaster (6 times!), General Board member, and finally as a President. I notice with pleasure that the efforts of the generations of Eurodocers do not evanesce but sum up to a considerable extent making the NGO stronger each year. Today Eurodoc is in good "shape" due to its vigorous community based on values, connecting both current volunteers and alumni. For instance, there are quite a few organisations where the advisory board plays such a vital role so naturally, being a living organisational memory and I thank **Agnieszka, Eva, Farouk, Giulia, Iryna, Margaux, and Mathias** for their active commitment and availability!

I cordially thank all the members of the Secretariat - our Working Group Coordinators and Officers and especially **Pil and Anna**, who performed tons of heavy lifting in such an elegant manner that it might seem a piece of cake for the uninitiated.

It was a pleasure and honor to lead the current Board as the team was full of bright and committed individuals who do care about a fair and sustainable research culture in Europe and beyond. Many thanks to **Hannah, Danila, Nicola, Joanna, and Patrizia** for the great job they did! I hope all of them stay in the next Administration in some capacity.

Very special thanks go to **Sebastian**, the Vice President, who effectively represented Eurodoc where I wasn't able to and led many crucial tasks throughout the term. I wish him the best of luck in running for the Presidency 2023/2024 as I am sure that his strong vision and dedication will be key assets for the organisation in the future.

Last but not least, I highly appreciate the support of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, as well as my native RMU, and its Head **Olesia**. Thanks and stay safe!

In my final words, let me wish success to the next Eurodoc administration and I look forward to our future exciting collaborations.

Best,

Oleksandr Berezko
Eurodoc President 2022/2023